

**MONITORING OF AIR QUALITY INDEX CHANGE IN TERRITORY IN
THE ARAL SEA REGION**

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Abstract:

In this paper, we have analyzed the air pollution change observed in the Aral Sea Region.

Keywords: Aral Sea, salinity, soil, CO₂.

Introduction:

The Aral separated into two water bodies after 1985: a “Small” Aral Sea in the north and a “Large” Aral Sea in the south. The Syr Darya flows into the former and the Amu Darya into the latter. Between 1960 and January 2006, the level of the Small Aral fell by 13 m and the Large Aral fell by 23 m. A channel (river) has connected the two lakes, with flow from the Small to the Large Aral. This flow has been primarily during the spring/early summer period when discharge from the Syr Darya to the Small Aral is greatest. During most of the year, the flow is much less and it often entirely ceases. The area of both seas taken together diminished by 74% and the volume by 90%.

Fig 1: Water Level of Aral Sea changes over the years

MODIS real-time satellite imagery shows that by late 2000-2013, the Large Aral Sea became every year decreasing. Efforts to partially restore/preserve the Small Aral Sea are underway. The World Bank and the government of Kazakhstan completed an 85 million USD project in fall 2005 that created a 13-km dike to block the flow from the Small to Large Aral Seas (Micklin 2005) Because of heavier-than-expected winter inflow to the Small Aral from the Syr Darya, the level has risen much more rapidly than expected (Greenberg 2006, Pala 2006).

Fig 2: How to change the Aral Sea from 2000 to 2013, shot from space, NASA.

A characteristic feature of the Aral Sea region's climate today, the (the term Aral Sea region, or another name Aral region stands for the geographic location of the Aral Sea and the surrounding area within a radius of 500km) - distinctly continental. In recent years, due to the process of the Aral Sea drying change in climatic conditions of Central Asia has been marked. Earlier Aral acted as a kind of regulator mitigating cold winds coming in the autumn and winter from Siberia and reducing the heat effect in the summer months like a giant air conditioner. With tightening of the climate the summer in the region has become more dry and short, winters - long and cold. These changes are also reflected in the report of IPCC AR5. A characteristic feature of the Aral region climate is the high repeatability and long duration of dust storms. There often strong winds in the Aral Sea region. The maximum wind speed can reach 20-25 m/s. The drying up of the Aral Sea has brought about a process of double desertification. One is due to the appearance of the dried bottom of the sea, the second-artificial waterlogging of irrigated lands. As a result, in the center of the belt of Karakum and Kyzylkum deserts formed another new desert "Aralkum" where the danger is represented by appearance of continuous saline lands consisting of fine marine sediments and residues of mineral deposits washed from irrigated fields. It marked a new stage of desertification impact to the process of ecosystem degradation of the Aral Sea area, regional and global climate. The seabed that in the former natural state served as a kind of desalination factory, now acts as an artificial man-made volcano emits into the atmosphere a huge mass of salt and pathological dust. The effect of pollution is amplified by the fact that the Aral Sea is located on the route of a powerful jet airstream from west to east. This facilitates the rise of aerosols in the upper layers and the rapid dissemination in the Earth's atmosphere.

Results

Assessment of the degree of salinity in the region.

In this part of the article, we will analyze the effect of water from the Aral Sea and the Amu Darya on the degree of salinization of crop areas, their causes and

consequences. Under saline soil we mean soil with a salt content of 0.25-0.30%. Saline soils are mainly distributed in semidesert and desert regions and alluvial plains downstream. Saline soils near the Aral Sea mainly consist of the salts of the anions Cl⁻, SO₄⁻, CO₃⁻, HCO₃⁻, and cations Ca⁺⁺, Mg⁺⁺, Na⁺ formed as a result of mutual reaction in an equivalent volume. We will try to analyze the process of soil salinity in the Aral region:

The degree of salinization of the total irrigated area of the territory of the Republic of Karakalpakstan located in the Aral region is shown in Fig 9. We will analyze the degree of salinity by dividing it into four classifications of WS (weak salinity), MS (medium salinity), HS (high salinity) and NS (no salinity). It is known that in recent years in the region there has been a process of dramatic reduction of useful non-salt sowing areas due to complete salinity of soil of different degree on the irrigated lands of the region. The lowest soil salinity was observed in 1981-1990 (WS-35.3, MS-30.9, HS-4.9, NS-28.9, 1990 WS-36.6, MS-40.2, HS-16.7, NS-6.5 in the 1980s) and by 1998, non-salted sowing area in percent was zero (1998 WS-56.5, MS-33.7, HS-9.8, NS-0) and this process was also repeated in 2000-2010 (2000 WS-58.7, MS -31.7, HS-9.6, NS-0, 2010 WS-48.7, MS-38.4, HS-12.9, NS-0).

Fig 1. Degree of salinity of irrigated lands in Aral region in %

A sharp increase in soil salinity in the Aral region can be theoretically and practically justified as follows. Firstly, a certain amount of salt is contained in the irrigation water supplied to irrigated fields, and eventually this whole salt is collected on the upper soil layer. For the years under review, the observed increases in water salinity

from the Amu Darya River (Fig. 10), the only source for providing clean drinking water to the Republic of Karakalpakstan, is the main indicator of the salinization of irrigated land in the region.

Fig 2. Dynamics of average annual mineralization of water in the Amu Darya River from 1960 to 2010

When comparing the results, it was found that the degree of mineralization of the northern part of the Amu Darya River in the Aral Sea region in 2000-2001 (1.66-1.26 g/l) had the highest rates, and in 2002-2010 it varied between 1.05-1.27 (g/l).

First: salt deposits on withered lakes and reservoirs due to wind spread to the nearest areas, and thereby salinize the soil surface. As evidence of this theory, as an example, we can cite a large saline field, formed due to the drying out of the Aral Sea. Beginning in 1960, the water level in the Aral Sea began to fall and the scale of the saline and sandy areas began to expand and the level of salinity of the sea water reached 9.93-98.6 g/l (1960-2010), and due to the increase in wind speed in the region by a 25- 50 m/s, this is also affected by the increase in saline areas.

Second: The direction and intensity of the physical, physico-chemical and biological processes occurring in the soil composition are mutually related to the temperature on the soil surface. As a result of the maximum increase in air temperature in the Aral region in the summer months to 40-45⁰C, a parallel increase in soil temperature is naturally observed, and this in turn affects the increase in the solubility of salts and the acceleration of the chemical reaction, soil layers change in moisture, air movement and its direction. Also, the development of microorganisms, biochemical processes and the separation of organic substances are accelerating.

Third: As a result of an increase in the mineralization level of the groundwater composition, the rise of groundwater to the upper layers of the soil through capillary tubes and their evaporation, salts in their composition are deposited in the root parts of plants and lead to soil salinity. The volume of groundwater mineralization in the western part of the Republic of Uzbekistan (the lower reaches of Zarafshan, Kashadarya, Syr Darya, Amu Darya, western part of Central Kyzylkum) is high and firm (State Agency for Standardization of the Republic of Uzbekistan). Along the course of large rivers (Amu Darya and irrigation canals), underground lenses with fresh water and used as drinking water in the Khorezm region and the Republic of Karakalpakstan are highly mineralized and hard, and therefore far from meeting the requirements and standards for drinking water. In the territory of Karakalpakstan nutrients (nitrogen, phosphorus) and pesticides in the collector-drainage water are very high in comparison with the ground waters. For comparison, the level of mineralization in the composition of underground water is 1.8-9 g/l, and in ground waters this figure is 0-1.2 g/l. This indicator, according to the above theory, is another factor in the salinization of soil in this region.

Analysis the level of air pollution in the Aral region: According to the data from the ESRL's database, the Global Monitoring Division, when the volume of CO₂ in the period after 1960 was analyzed in the territory of the Republic of Uzbekistan (Fig. 11), the volume of its concentration increased by 10.6% (1960 – 316,91 ppm, 1990 – 354,39). Over the past 24 years, from 1991 to 2016, the concentration of CO₂ increased by 11.4% (1991 356.45 ppm, 2016 400.83), it means, it steadily grows every year in the range of 0,2-0,8 %. If to connect the reason for the increase in the level of air pollution with anthropogenic factors, this can be attributed to the large scale of growth in the production industry in Uzbekistan, namely, the commissioning of several chemical and transport hubs in Chirchik, Okhangaran, Fergana Valley, Surkhandarya, Kashkadarya, Zarafshan (towns and regions of Uzbekistan). The fast development of the production sector negatively affects the environment, in particular air pollution. Due to the fact that the industrial cities listed above are

mainly located in mountain valleys, the process of self-purification of air is rather limited, that is, mountain winds drive polluted air to foothill areas, which means stagnation of polluted air in these foothill cities.

Another major factor in increasing air pollution in the territory of Uzbekistan is a continuing catastrophe with the Aral Sea. At present, the dried bottom of the Aral Sea extends to 26,000 km². Two-thirds of this territory is saline and consists of saline sandy areas. According to the State Meteorological Committee, it is from these areas that millions of tons of sand and dust spread to all parts of the Aral Sea. These are still particles that can be caught with the eye. From the bottom of the Aral Sea, 5 million tons of fine dust and salt that are not visible to the eye are distributed annually, which was proved by new studies of the Academy of Sciences of Uzbekistan. The dried bottom of the Aral Sea becomes the main source of aerosols emitting into the Earth's atmosphere. Propagation through the air of these solid very small particles is impassive. Particles of salt and sand rising from the bottom of the Aral Sea with ease overcome the flat mountains of Ustyurt, and spread to the south and west, and reach the Caspian region. Especially these dust and salt particles pose a danger to glaciers. Because the glaciers are exactly on the way of passage of salt storms. In this regard, in all the lands around the Aral region, the mineralization of rainwater has almost doubled in recent times, almost 7 times in the area in the immediate vicinity of the Aral Sea. Due to the parts of salt and sand rising from the help of winds from the bottom of the dried Aral Sea, the Earth's atmosphere is polluted more than 5%. The tragedy of the Aral Sea has changed the current climate. Earlier, the Aral Sea regulated the temperature and humidity of the air in the region in a particular way.

Fig 3. Change carbon dioxide CO₂ territory in Uzbekistan from 1970 to 2016 year. (Source: NOAA's Earth System Research Laboratory (ESRL), Global Monitoring Division)

Fig 4. Compare between carbon dioxide CO₂ and radiation balance from 1970 to 2016 year.

The Republic of Karakalpakstan in the north of Uzbekistan is the closest region to the Aral Sea (42,460 N., 59,730 E). Its economy is mainly connected with the agrarian sector. Given the fact that the production of organic combustible materials (coal, oil, gas), the main factor of growth in the atmosphere of carbon dioxide, is relatively smaller than in other regions, we can see that the influence of the anthropogenic factor on air pollution in the region is not big. The observed increase in the concentration of CO² in the territory of Uzbekistan also partially belongs to the territory of Karakalpakstan located in the Aral Sea region and in its turn the ecological catastrophe observed around the Aral has a significant negative effect on

the pollution of atmospheric air in the territory of Uzbekistan. Based on the data shown in Figure 12, the mutual correlation relationship between the two parameters was analyzed using the example of the Aral region and, based on the results, we can see that in 2011-2016 it equaled ($r = 0.8$) and in 2005-2010. ($R = 0.4$) was the most positively close result and in 1970-1975 the lowest negative correlation ($r = -0.7$). The above-used radiation balance was calculated on the basis of data obtained from the meteorological stations located on the territory of the Republic of Karakalpakstan. It has also been shown that the stable growth of CO₂ concentration over the past years has been associated with solar radiation. The rise in air temperature around the Aral Sea over many years has also led to an increase in the radiation balance in the region, and will remain the main factor for the growth of CO₂ concentration in the atmosphere.

References:

- [1] Aitekeyeva, N., Li, X., Guo, H., Wu, W., Shirazi, Z., Ilyas, S., . . . Hategekimana, Y. (2020). Drought Risk Assessment in Cultivated Areas of Central Asia Using MODIS Time-Series Data. *Water*, 12(6). doi:10.3390/w12061738
- [2] Begjanova, Z., Karajonova, A., Nietullaeva, S., N Abdullaev, N., & Jarasov, A. (2021). *Spatial hydrological GIS analysis in the Aral Sea Basin*. Paper presented at the Збірник наукових праць SCIENTIA., Sidney, Australia.
- [3] Berdimbetov, T., Ilyas, S., Ma, Z., Bilal, M., & Nietullaeva, S. (2021). Climatic Change and Human Activities Link to Vegetation Dynamics in the Aral Sea Basin Using NDVI. *Earth Systems and Environment*, 5(2), 303-318. doi:10.1007/s41748-021-00224-7
- [4] Berdimbetov, T., Ma, Z.-G., Shelton, S., Ilyas, S., & Nietullaeva, S. (2021). Identifying Land Degradation and its Driving Factors in the Aral Sea Basin From 1982 to 2015. *Frontiers in Earth Science*, 9. doi:10.3389/feart.2021.690000
- [5] Berdimbetov, T. T., Ma, Z.-G., Liang, C., & Ilyas, S. (2020). Impact of Climate Factors and Human Activities on Water Resources in the Aral Sea Basin. *Hydrology*, 7(2). doi:10.3390/hydrology7020030
- [6] Berdimbetov, T. T., Zhu-Guo, M., Nietullaeva, S., & Yegizbayeva, A. (2021). Analysis of Impact of Aral Sea Catastrophe on Anomaly Climate Variables and Hydrological Processes. *Elsevier, International Journal of*

- Geoinformatics*, 17(1).
doi:<https://journals.sfu.ca/ijg/index.php/journal/article/view/1711>
- [7] Bohovic, R., Dobrovolny, P., & Klein, D. (2017). The Spatial and Temporal Dynamics of Remotely-sensed Vegetation Phenology in Central Asia in the 1982–2011 Period. *European Journal of Remote Sensing*, 49(1), 279-299. doi:10.5721/EuJRS20164916
- [8] de Beurs, K. M., Henebry, G. M., Owsley, B. C., & Sokolik, I. (2015). Using multiple remote sensing perspectives to identify and attribute land surface dynamics in Central Asia 2001–2013. *Remote Sensing of Environment*, 170, 48-61. doi:10.1016/j.rse.2015.08.018
- [9] Karajonova, A., Begjanova, Z., Berdimbetova, A., Juginisov, A., & Madreimov, S. *Vegetation change analysis using NDVI in the Aral Sea Basin*. Paper presented at the I International Scientific and Theoretical Conference «CURRENT ISSUES OF SCIENCE, PROSPECTS AND CHALLENGES», Sydney, Australia
- [10] Lioubimtseva, E. (2014). Impact of Climate Change on the Aral Sea and Its Basin. In *The Aral Sea* (pp. 405-427).
- [11] Lioubimtseva, E., & Cole, R. (2007). Uncertainties of Climate Change in Arid Environments of Central Asia. *Reviews in Fisheries Science*, 14(1-2), 29-49. doi:10.1080/10641260500340603
- [12] Micklin, P. (2007). The Aral Sea Disaster. *Annual Review of Earth and Planetary Sciences*, 35(1), 47-72. doi:10.1146/annurev.earth.35.031306.140120
- [13] Nietullaeva, S., Fayzullaev, B., Karimova, A., & Shaudenbayev, N. (2021). An Investigation into the Hydro-Climate Processes Impacting Aral Sea Region in Central Asia. *Annals of the Romanian Society for Cell Biology*, 25(4), 11692–11703. doi:<https://www.annalsofrscb.ro/index.php/journal/article/view/3991>
- [14] Oteniyazov, R. I., Xujakulov, T. A., Seytniyazov, D. B., & Atamuratov, A. T. (2020). Modeling the water resources contamination level in open nodes. *European Journal of Molecular & Clinical Medicine*, 7(7).